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ULTIMATE HADRON-BEAM BRIGHTNESS

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ABSTRACT

The activity of Task 5.2 “Pushing Accelerator Frontiers” (PAF) supports the community effort in pushing the hadron-beam brightness. Bright hadron beams are fundamental for atomic and nuclear physics experiments as well as for achieving novel ultra-precise nuclear clocks (HITHOR). Multi-species beams in storage rings are foreseen as a novel intriguing possibility for collisions in a moving frame, and new insights into nuclear reactions. Space-charge forces and intra-beam scattering are two fundamental mechanisms that limit the ultimate beam brightness. Pushing Accelerator Frontiers has co-organized the “Space Charge 2024” workshop where the state of the art in this domain has been reviewed.

I.FAST Consortium, 2025

For more information on IFAST, its partners, and contributors, please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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1 Executive summary

This report focuses on the results of the Space Charge Workshop held in Dongguan and on ongoing initiatives aimed at achieving ultimate hadron-beam brightness. The demand for higher-brightness hadron beams spans several key facilities, including the storage rings at GSI (ESR, CRYRING), the future HESR ring at FAIR, CERN's accelerator complex (LEIR, PSB, PS, SPS, LHC), and the Lanzhou rings at the IMP facility in China. CERN also operates the AD and ELENA rings for low-energy antiprotons, while the HIAF project in China plans constructing the SRing for storing exotic beams. Producing high-brightness beams in these existing and future accelerators presents significant challenges, including limitations from lattice structures, beam intensity, intrabeam scattering (IBS), and collective effects. Brightness can be enhanced through advanced injection techniques—such as two or three-plane injection schemes (HIAF, GSI)—while space charge and resonance effects are being managed via lattice optimization and space-charge compensation strategies (e.g., at J-PARC). Collective effects are mitigated using chromaticity control and feedback systems. Emittance growth due to IBS is addressed through active beam cooling techniques, including electron, stochastic, and laser cooling, implemented in accelerator facilities at GSI, CERN, and HIAF. The report also highlights the global deployment of these technologies. Additionally, we sketch the progress on advanced concepts such as optical stochastic cooling, currently tested at Fermilab's IOTA facility, and laser cooling developments at GSI. Finally, we conclude with a discussion of the roadmap towards achieving the ultimate beam brightness.

2 Brightness limitations of hadron beams

The ultimate goal of hadron beam production is to bring ions into collision with a fixed target or with another beam. A high-brightness beam is connected to luminosity, and the higher the luminosity, the more collisions occur. Brightness is defined as the beam current “ I ” divided by the 4D phase space volume occupied by the beam. Therefore, a high-brightness beam requires a large beam current in a small phase space volume. Producing high-brightness beams is challenging mainly due to the repulsive Coulomb force among the hadron particles. The electric fields created by many particles generate a space-charge effect that opposes the focusing forces of the accelerator. This effect includes both incoherent and coherent responses. The unavoidable nonlinearities of the accelerator couple with the space charge, causing either a rapid coherent beam response or a slow incoherent increase in emittance, due to the interaction between amplitude-dependent detuning and magnet error resonances. These mechanisms complicate the production of a high-density beam and hinder maintaining it over time without special mitigation techniques.

Coulomb forces originate from point-like charged particles. During beam production, creating small phase space volumes inevitably increases the beam's intrinsic collisionality with other particles—a process known as intrabeam scattering (IBS). This fundamental process results in Coulomb collisions that exchange energy and momentum among particles, transferring potential and kinetic energies within different parts of the phase space. Over time, IBS causes emittance growth or "heating," which reduces the beam's brightness. Without cooling techniques, achieving ultimate brightness is impossible.

The transition from intrabeam scattering between individual ion pairs and ion motion in the coarse-grained Coulomb potential of the particle ensemble is not captured by most of the accelerator simulation codes or the corresponding analytical descriptions.

For physics based on storage rings, the ultimate brightness is of the main actors in the global scenario are the storage rings of GSI (ESR, CRYRING), along with the future HESR part of the FAIR plan, the rings at CERN (LEIR, PSB, PS, SPS, LHC) as well as the IMP China facility with the Lanzhou storage rings. CERN also features the AD and ELENA with antiprotons at low energy. In addition, the HIAF project in China foresees the construction of the SRing for the storage of exotic beams.

Because of the broad and joint interest of both IMP and IHEP in China, and also the “Helmholtz Forschungsakademie für FAIR” (HFHF), the Pushing Accelerator Frontiers task of iFAST co-organized, in September 2024, the international Space Charge 2024 workshop in Dongguan, China.

3 Coherent and incoherent effects of space charge

At HIAF, it is planned to deliver intense beams to targets. The SRing will be realized through linac acceleration and two-plane injection into the Bring [1]. The design intensity is 2.0×10^{11} ppp, which will be accelerated in a cutting-edge facility with a fast-ramping rate of 12 T/s and a high repetition rate of 3-5 Hz. The beam will be longitudinally stacked when transferring from the Bring to SRing. In these rings, the effect of the incoherent space charge in the presence of lattice nonlinearities is critical, especially in view of the potential 4th-order structure resonances driven by space charge in the Bring, as is illustrated in Fig. 1

Fig.1. Fourth-order structure resonances predicted by the CISP simulation for the HIAF Bring [1].

The strategy for mitigating the space charge effect is to employ a high, fast ramping mode, 12T/s, $\pm 38,000$ A/s, with a peak power of ± 230 MW at full load, relying on new technology based on a MA (Magnetic alloy) RF system [1], as is illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig.2. Schematic of the concept and network implementation of the MA core for the HIAF BRing [1].

At JPARC, the RCS relies on the H⁻ multiturn injection. This machine is highly space-charge dominated, which poses a serious obstacle to fulfilling multiple demands simultaneously. Routine operation with 1 MW has started at the MLF since April 2024. The space charge and resonance effects complicate simultaneous beam optimizations at high intensities. Systematic beam studies and numerical simulations are conducted for the optimisation of many parameters and their pulse-by-pulse switching to minimise beam loss and beam emittance at both the RCS/MLF and the MR. The incoherent space charge tunespread is ~0.5, and this large a spread leads to an overlap with important machine resonances, leading to beam degradation and beam loss. The major resonances in the RCS are

- 1) $Q_x - 2Q_y = -6$, which is a structure resonance excited by the sextupole field component intrinsic to the bending magnets (BMs): $K_2 = 0.1006 \text{ m}^{-2}$ (1/4 strength of full x correction). This resonance affects operation at lower beam energies due to the large tune spread. It also produces larger emittance growth in the vertical plane. For the MLF beam, this resonance is corrected by sextupoles, as the latter are not being used for chromaticity correction.
- 2) $3Q_x = 19$ is a 3rd order random resonance excited by the not-cancelled sextupole field component ($K_2 = 0.0012 \text{ m}^{-2}$) in the injection chicane magnets (SB). This resonance causes horizontal emittance growth when the SBs are ON during the beam injection. The effect can be partially mitigated by reducing the magnetic fields of the SB by 20%.
- 3) $Q_x + 2Q_y = 19$ is a 3rd order random resonance that arises from the sextupole fields in the BMs and chromatic correction sextupole magnets. It is also additionally excited by a distortion of the lattice super-periodicity due to a beta beating caused by the chicane during injection. It leads to twice larger emittance growth in the vertical plane. Currently, $\Delta\beta/\beta \sim 10\%$ as Q_y is set far from the $Q_y = 6.5$, and the beating is further decreased by reducing SB fields.
- 4) The Montague resonance $2Q_x - 2Q_y = 0$ is a 4th-order systematic resonance excited by skew-quadrupole errors, the 2nd-order effect of the sextupolar field, and also by the octupole component in the space charge field. It is critical when Q_x and Q_y are close to each other. This resonance causes an emittance exchange between the horizontal and vertical planes. Its effect is mitigated with a careful choice of injection painting. The anti-correlated painting is favourable for a larger transverse painting [2].

The 3-GeV RCS of J-PARC shows that the space charge effect at injection energy excites many resonances, resulting in beam emittance growth and beam losses. Beam handling, machine properties, and errors have been incorporated into the simulations in order to obtain precise results, allowing the identification of each resonance effect and developing the corresponding countermeasures. Recently, the SC effect has been sufficiently mitigated at 1 MW operation by combining several appropriate measures. The beam loss and the beam emittance have been minimized. The residual beam loss of 1 MW is $\ll 0.1\%$ and this loss occurs almost entirely during the injection period, where about half of the total loss is attributed to the foil scattering. The beam loss power at the collimator is ~ 0.1 kW (small compared with the collimator capacity of 4 kW). The simulation results are well consistent with the measurements. Improvements of the RCS beam quality have also been well recognized at the downstream facilities. The machine activation is well suppressed, achieving a sustainable operation with more than 98% availability.

Another important task to reach a high-brightness beam is the injection. The development of an efficient method to accumulate as much beam as possible is necessary. The standard approach to inject a hadron beam from a linac into a synchrotron is via a multi-turn injection. This approach is usually implemented in one plane and requires the creation of a local bump to fill the horizontal phase space up to the machine acceptance. For proton and ion multiturn injection via magnetic or electrostatic septum, Liouville's theorem applies and severely restricts the number of turns, typically to ~ 15 turns for single plane injection with optimized conditions. The specific results depend on the machine acceptance and the emittance of the injected beam coming from the linac. To increase the brightness also the vertical plane can be exploited, increasing the number of injected turns to ~ 100 . At HIAF, the two-plane injection scheme is studied and will be implemented for the BRing [3]. They estimate a 20% beam loss over 100 turn injection to achieve a stable intensity of 1.3×10^{10} particles. Figure 3 shows a simulation of the full process.

x-y real space evolution

Fig. 3. Two-plane injection at HIAF from a multiparticle simulation obtained via CISP-GPU [3].

At GSI, the demand for increasing the brightness is also pushing the studies for the implementation of the two-plane injection, as is illustrated in Fig. 4.

In general, horizontal-longitudinal and three-dimensional x-y-z injection schemes are also feasible. These can be implemented with a nonzero dispersion at the injection point by varying the beam energy from the linac.

Fig. 4. Characteristic efficiency of the standard multiturn injection. [4]. Two-plane injection studies at GSI [5]; the study shows the dependence of a two-plane injection scheme efficiency as a function of the machine working point.

At CERN, the LHC Injector Upgrade greatly increased the beam brightness and pushed the intensity. The space charge force is limiting the emittance in the PSB, the PS, and in the SPS, as is illustrated in Fig. 5. Resonance crossing is the mechanism behind beam loss or emittance growth caused by space charge in all these machines. In PS and SPS, the space charge condition is applied in the form $\Delta Q_y < 0.31, 0.21$, respectively. These limits were found empirically. Ideally, they should both be near 0.25 (i.e. the space available between the 0.25 and integer resonances), but due to uncertainty in the beam distributions and width of the stop bands, plus possible influence from other resonance lines (e.g., the coupling resonance line) the values chosen seem to better represent the actual limits in the two accelerators under some simplified assumptions.

In Fig. 5, the rounded shape of the curves approaches zero, followed by a linear behaviour is because for very low emittances the dispersive part of the beam transverse size dominates, while for larger emittances it is the emittance part. PS and SPS have both bunch-to-bucket injection. On the other hand, in the PSB, the beam is injected by H^- charge exchange and chopped longitudinally from Linac4 over several turns. The “brightness line” shown is the best line that can be measured, and it also roughly fits the simulation of the injection process. In reality, the line should reduce its slope for low intensities (when the emittance blow-up becomes dominated by the scattering on the stripping foil) and eventually level off to $0.4 \mu\text{m}$ even for the limit of zero intensity (because this is the emittance from Linac4). This is indicated by the green curve in Fig. 5.

The so-called 8b4e bunch pattern, consisting of trains of 8 bunches spaced by 25 ns, followed by 4 “empty” 25-ns buckets, is limited by space charge in the SPS and, therefore, is expected to perform exactly like the bunch compression, merging, and splitting (“BCMS”) scheme.

In mid-August 2025, a normalised rms emittance of $\leq 1.5 \mu\text{m}$ was measured at PS extraction with 2.6×10^{11} protons per bunch extracted, consistent with the diagram, and also with measurements right at SPS injection. Under the LHC Injector Upgrade program, PS longitudinal instabilities have been successfully overcome by installing a wide-band longitudinal feedback system (Finemet cavity) and reducing the impedance of the 10 MHz RF system. Hence, the limit corresponding to the vertical red line in Fig.5 has been removed. At present, more than 3×10^{11} protons per bunch can stably be extracted from the PS in trains of 72 bunches. The requirement on the longitudinal emittance, however, which should be small enough not to exceed the bunch length of 3.8 ns at the SPS injection (for ensuring horizontal beam stability in the SPS), makes intensities above 2.9×10^{11} protons per bunch hardly usable.

Fig. 5. Space charge limitations in the CERN injector complex translated to intensity and emittance at the LHC injection (G. Rumolo, 2025)

4 Collective effects

To simulate collective instabilities, the HIAF team developed a CISP code, which may run on a conventional CPU as well as on a GPU cluster. CISP can deal with 10^8 macroparticles and split the beam into 10^5 beam slices to allow studying the interaction between ultra-short wakes and ultra-long bunches, and many other multi-dynamics multi-scale coupling effects. The broadband impedances from a 3D-printed titanium alloy cage-supported vacuum chamber in the Bring are included in the CISP-GPU instability simulations. This instability is stabilized by a large negative chromaticity $\xi = -5$ and by a wideband feedback system with a bandwidth larger than 500 MHz (see Ref. [1]).

Instabilities are of significant concern in all high-intensity hadron facilities. The Rapid Cycling Synchrotron of the CSNS is also affected by an instability. The increase in the facility beam power towards the target value of 140 kW led to horizontal instabilities arising about 8 ms after injection, which worsen for higher intensity. The instability growth rate is less than 1 ms. See Fig. 6. Only the coupled bunch mode of 1 has been observed. The beam behaviour of a single bunch is similar to that of two bunches with the same beam intensity. A similar instability was also observed in the vertical plane when the power was further increased. It disappears when the beam power is lowered to 100 kW; see Ref. [6]. With the help of a sextupole, the beam power could be raised to 160 kW.

Fig. 6. The horizontal instability in the CSNS RCS (red) and the effect of the mitigation (blue) obtained by optimising the tune (moved below the half integer) and the chromaticity.

A big effort is invested in identifying the source of the impedance, and through a dedicated campaign, it has been recognized that the RF shield on the ceramic chambers is responsible for the instability. Simulations including this impedance yield a consistent beam behaviour. The impedance of all chambers in the RCS has been assessed, revealing that the machine impedance is excessively large [6].

5 Intrabeam Scattering and mitigation measures: beam cooling

The effect of intrabeam scattering is countered by beam cooling: the current state of this mitigation method has been reported by Markus Steck [7]. High brightness results from tightly confining the phase space volume occupied by the beam, despite the unavoidable influence of Coulomb collisions. The similarity between this process and collision dynamics in molecular gases makes it natural to introduce the concept of temperature for particle beams in an accelerator. In gases, temperature is defined by the rms kinetic energy spread of a single molecule, which relates to the phase space volume it occupies; similarly, the beam's temperature can be understood and linked to its phase space volume (a concept that can be precisely defined in an rms sense). Over time, the beam's phase space volume inevitably expands during storage; therefore, methods to "shrink" the beam phase space volume are desirable. The challenge in developing these methods is to overcome Liouville's theorem, which states that the volume of an ensemble of copies of a Hamiltonian system remains constant throughout its time evolution. Strictly speaking, a particle beam does not satisfy Liouville's theorem because all particles are influenced by Coulomb forces, making only the full beam the relevant Hamiltonian system for the theorem, rather than its individual particles. However, if the beam density is very high—meaning many particles are within the Debye sphere—the forces on each particle are dominated by the smooth Coulomb component; thus, Liouville's theorem still approximately applies. In this situation, conventional beam cooling methods cannot be used to reduce the beam's temperature. Instead, beam cooling techniques modify the beam's properties by transferring the

random (thermal) energy of the particles to an external medium. The two main cooling methods are Electron Cooling and Stochastic Cooling. Table 1 presents a summary of the current status of these devices in accelerator laboratories worldwide.

Electron Cooling Systems

NAP-M, Novosibirsk, Russia, 1974
 ICE-Ring, CERN, Switzerland, 1979
 Test Ring, Fermilab, Chicago, USA, 1980
 LEAR, CERN, Switzerland, 1987
 IUCF Cooler, Bloomington, Indiana, 1988
 TSR, Heidelberg, Germany, 1988 and 2004
 TARN II, Tokyo, Japan, 1989
 CELSIUS, Uppsala, Sweden, 1989
 ESR, GSI, Darmstadt, Germany, 1990
 ASTRID, Aarhus, Denmark, 1992
 CRYRING, Stockholm, Sweden, 1992, now at GSI
 COSY, Jülich, Germany, 1993 and 2013
 SIS18, GSI, Darmstadt, Germany, 1998
 Antiproton Decelerator (AD), CERN, 1998
 HIMAC, Chiba, Japan, 2000
 LEIR, CERN, Switzerland, 2005
 Recycler, Fermilab, Chicago, USA, 2005
 S-LSR, Kyoto, Japan, 2005
 CSRm, IMP Lanzhou, China, 2005
 CSRe, IMP Lanzhou, China, 2008

ELENA, CERN, Switzerland, 2018
 CSR, Heidelberg, Germany, 2019
 LEReC, BNL, Brookhaven, USA, 2019
 NICA Booster, Dubna, Russia, 2021
 NICA Collider, Dubna, Russia
 HIAF, Huizhou, China
 EIC, BNL, Brookhaven, USA
 IOTA, Fermilab, USA
 FAIR, Darmstadt, Germany

ESR, GSI, Darmstadt, Germany, 1995
 Antiproton Decelerator (AD), CERN, 1998
 Recycler, Fermilab, Chicago, USA, 2005
 RHIC, BNL, Brookhaven, USA, 2006
 CSRe, IMP, Lanzhou, China, 2008
 IOTA, Fermilab, USA, 2022 OSC
 NICA, Dubna, Russia
 HIAF, Huizhou, China
 FAIR, Darmstadt, Germany

Stochastic Cooling Systems

ICE-Ring, CERN, Switzerland, 1979
 Test Ring, Fermilab, Chicago, USA, 1980
 NAP-M, Novosibirsk, Russia 1981
 ACOL, AA, CERN, Switzerland, 1983
 Debuncher, Accumulator, FNAL, Chicago, USA, 1983
 TARN II, Tokyo, Japan, 1983
 LEAR, CERN, Switzerland, 1987
 COSY, Jülich, 1993

Status
 decommissioned
 in operation
 planned

Table 1: Status of the Electron and Stochastic cooling systems worldwide [7].

5.1 ELECTRON COOLING

A schematic of the electron cooling is shown in Fig. 7. The method relies on creating an electron beam with a cold temperature, which travels at the same velocity as the storage particle beam. The two beams overlap for some path length, and so a process of “heat” exchange takes place. In this way, the transverse beam thermal energy is transferred to the cold electron beam.

Fig. 7. Left. Schematic of the electron cooling principle. Right. Cooling at the ESR [7].

The equilibrium between the IBS growth rate and the cooling growth rate gives the lowest beam temperature achievable.

$$\tau = \frac{3}{8\sqrt{2}\pi n_e Q^2 r_e r_i c L_C} \left(\frac{k_B T_e}{m_e c^2} + \frac{k_B T_i}{m_i c^2} \right)^{3/2} \quad \tau_{\text{IBS}}^{-1} = \frac{q^4 e^4}{(A m_i)^2} \cdot \frac{N}{C \epsilon_h \epsilon_v \delta p / p} \cdot \frac{1}{(\gamma^4 \beta^3 c^3)} \cdot 4\pi L_C^{\text{IBS}}$$

The formula on the left yields the inverse cooling rate, while the second the IBS heating rate. The equilibrium temperature, hence the equilibrium beam emittance, is obtained when $\tau = \tau_{\text{IBS}}$. The dependence on all parameters and processes makes this estimate challenging, especially in peculiar accelerator conditions, for example, when close to the transition energy. Therefore, the complex beam dynamics requires a multiparticle simulation, including the Coulomb smooth field and the collisionality, as a necessary tool to predict the beam behaviour during the production of extremely bright beams. This effort is also carried out jointly with the HFHF academy [8] by supporting the development of a 3D PIC MPI parallel solver that enables the inclusion of an enhanced model of Coulomb collisionality. The aim is to model the effect of IBS in operational scenarios, especially in challenging ones such as near the transition. iFAST has supported a benchmarking of this software development with a mirror development at the CSNS, where a new PIC solver has been developed for modelling high-intensity effects. The goal of the benchmarking is to compare the quality and predictions of the tracking over the long term, exceeding the usual time scale of a conventional PIC simulation. Here, the challenge is to contain the numerical artifact that may compete with the actual modelling of the particle-particle Coulomb collision in a beam. Figure 8 shows the ongoing efforts to benchmark 2 different 3D PIC codes.

Fig. 8. This picture shows the ongoing benchmarking between the HFHF-developed 3D PIC code [9] and the CSNS [10]. The HFHF code will help to simulate the brightness of the ESR beams at GSI. The benchmarking is carried out for a simplified ESR lattice (no FINT) and for a 3D bunched beam with rms emittances $\epsilon_x=3.9$ mm-mrad, $\epsilon_y=9.3$ mm-mrad, and the rms bunch length of 2.25 m. The simulation test is carried out for 10^{10} protons, which yields an incoherent tunes shift $\Delta Q_x = 0.04$, $\Delta Q_y=0.02$.

By properly reducing the beam density, an ultracold beam can be produced, as shown in Fig. 9. This technique has generated a linear ion chain in the ESR storage ring at GSI: a jump in the beam momentum spread clearly shows the change of beam regime.

Fig. 9. Left, Ultracold beam produced at GSI. Right, the ESR Electron Cooler [3].

The electron cooling is not only used to cool a single beam, but also to aid the accumulation of multiple injected beams: each beam injected into an accelerator via a standard multiturn injection gets cooled to damp its coherent oscillation, thereby improving the efficiency of the transverse injection and accumulation process.

The process of electron cooling has already been realised at high energies. Bunches of electrons are also employed at the Low-Energy RHIC electron Cooler (LEReC) of BNL. An extreme electron cooling is reached at the CSR, Heidelberg, where the beam in the cooling ring operates near the space charge and IBS limits.

5.2 STOCHASTIC COOLING

Figure 10 sketches the principle of stochastic cooling.

Fig. 10 Principle of stochastic cooling.

The principle of transverse cooling consists of measuring the deviation from the ideal orbit and using the signal for driving a correction kick (feedback). For the process to work, the travel time of the signal from the pick-up to the kicker has to be consistent with the number of betatron oscillations (it should be a quarter or three-quarters modulo an integer). Additionally, the process of cooling requires continuous mixing of the beam particles so as to transfer the thermal component of the particle motion to the coherent oscillation of the centre of mass that can be damped by the feedback system. In this way, a continuous, slow transfer of the thermal motion to the kicker (kicking the beam requires energy, which corresponds to the energy needed to remove the coherent beam oscillation created by the mixing). This process is unavoidably limited by the presence of noise in the signal detection and amplification.

Presently, the longitudinal cooling is achieved via: 1) Palmer cooling: here, the pick-up is placed in a dispersive section to detect the horizontal position; hence the acceleration/deceleration kick corrects the momentum deviation; 2) Notch filter cooling: the filter creates notches at the harmonics of the nominal revolution frequency; consequently, particles are forced to circulate at the nominal frequency; 3) ToF cooling is a simplified scheme without notches, which allows efficient pre-cooling.

The requirements for stochastic cooling are: 1) large bandwidth (typically one octave in the GHz range); 2) high sensitivity (high impedance) of pick-up and kickers; 3) low electronic noise (cold pick-ups, low noise amplifiers); 4) good transfer function in gain and phase; 5) large, but variable gain; 6) special ion optical properties of the ring, in particular: 6a) betatron phase advance between the transverse pick-up and kicker; 6b) small momentum slip factor (large wanted and little unwanted mixing); 6c) or Palmer cooling: large dispersion value at the pick-up.

At the moment, all stochastic cooling systems are limited by the available bandwidth (max. 8 GHz). Higher bandwidths are achievable with coherent electron cooling and with optical stochastic cooling.

5.3 ADVANCED SCHEMES

The advantages of stochastic cooling are particularly significant for colliders. At RHIC, the 3D stochastic cooling for Uranium-on-Uranium collisions has increased the integrated luminosity per store by a factor of 5. Often, the stochastic cooling is used in combination with electron cooling to reach the best beam performance.

The combination of electron and stochastic cooling is proposed for fast cooling at the highest energies through a novel scheme called the “Coherent Electron Cooling” system. The Coherent Electron Cooling system has three major subsystems. 1) modulator: the ions of the beam imprint a “density bump” on the electron distribution; 2) amplifier based on a high-gain free electron laser, on the microbunching instability, or a plasma cascade; each of these interactions amplifies a density bump by orders of magnitude; 3) kicker: the amplified & phase-shifted electron charge distribution is used to correct the velocity offset of the ions. Such a “strong hadron cooling” scheme is considered for possible deployment at the Electron Ion Collider (Fig. 11).

Fig. 11. The Electron Ion Collider. In this project, the brightness of the colliding beams is planned to be increased through advanced electron cooling systems.

The four main challenges for realizing Coherent Electron Cooling are: (1) high-current ERL, (2) a low-noise electron beam, (3) longitudinal alignment of 1 micron over 100 m distance, and (4) the controlled amplifier [11].

A concept similar to Coherent Electron Cooling is also used for the Optical Stochastic Cooling. Here, a Pickup Wiggler makes the beam emit synchrotron radiation, on which the characteristic features of the beam distribution are imprinted. The beam is transported through the accelerator, and at the same time, the radiation emitted by the beam at the Pickup Wiggler is amplified through an optical amplifier and then injected into a Kicker wiggler, where it interacts with the beam and applies the correction for cooling. This concept has been demonstrated with an electron beam at the IOTA facility in

Fermilab in 2022 (Fig. 12), and it is considered an interesting option for cooling hadron beams at the highest energy.

Fig. 12. Scheme of the optical stochastic demonstration [12].

Among the novel concepts for advanced cooling, Laser Cooling is now receiving attention as it is proposed as a main tool for experimental physics. In particular, a special laser cooling scheme for particular stripped ion beams is a key ingredient of the Gamma Factory project [13]. Laser cooling is also foreseen in the FAIR project. Figure 13 shows the Schottky noise during the laser sweep. In this picture, the relative frequency width is $df/f=2 \times 10^{-5}$

Fig. 13. Schottky spectra at the ESR, during laser cooling of C^{3+} . (left) and the Argon ion laser (257.3 nm), frequency doubled, utilized for this experiment (right).

The laser cooling is being prepared and set up for the SIS100 in a dedicated laser cooling area, also dedicated to laser spectroscopy [14].

6 The path towards the ultimate brightness

The path towards ultimate brightness requires:

- 1) The creation of a bright beam at the linac section. The injection to a synchrotron should minimize the dilution factor, and a non-Liouvillian injection method should be employed.
- 2) Controlling the effect of space charge on beam degradation. This is reached by resonance compensation and proper choice of the machine working point. Additionally, space charge compensation techniques could be developed, such as electron lenses and “electron columns” for space charge compensation. For specific mechanisms degrading the beam quality, such as the space charge-induced periodic crossing of resonances, the longitudinal bunch shaping via multi-harmonics RF systems may lead to significant benefit and greatly reduce the resulting beam loss.
- 3) Collective effects must be controlled via proper feedback systems and with proper design of components to stay within an acceptable impedance budget.
- 4) The Beam Cooling remains a fundamental tool to reach high-brightness beams. In particular, the future of beam cooling will be shaped by two types of development:
 - 1) Cooling at higher energies
 - Laser cooling in SIS100 is one example
 - The Electron-Ion Collider (EIC) will significantly benefit from beam cooling options:
 - electron beam from a linac (energy recovery linac)
 - coherent electron cooling
 - merging of electrons circulating in a storage ring
 - 2) The high brightness beam will be relevant for two emerging Heavy Ion and Secondary Beam Facilities: FAIR (Germany) and HIAF (China). These projects will need more traditional cooling systems, but operating over a large energy range and with a large particle variety.

The highest brightness could be achieved with 1D, 2D, or 3D crystalline beams. 3D crystalline beams up to helix structures surrounding a linear string were created at the RF quadrupole storage ring PALLAS in Germany [15].

An ion-cloud confined in a Paul trap acquires Coulomb crystalline state when cooled near absolute zero, the normalized emittance of a Coulomb crystal can be in the sub-femtometer range. Ongoing efforts at Hiroshima University aim at demonstrating an ultimate single-ion source with rms emittance of order 10^{-16} m from a two-component Coulomb crystal. Experiments have already generated a Coulomb crystal consisting of calcium and nitrogen ions. The image of a two-component Coulomb crystal taken by an intensified charge coupled device (ICCD) camera in Fig. 14. The bright area of

the outer part of the crystal is the laser-induced fluorescence from calcium ions. The dark area of the inner part is considered to include nitrogen ions, which do not emit light [16].

Fig. 14. Image of a two-component shell Coulomb crystal at Hiroshima University [16].

If the beam particles are bosons, e.g., He nuclei (alpha particles), potentially also a Bose-Einstein condensate could be generated through cooling; see Ref. [17] and articles cited therein.

7 Conclusion

Beam brightness is compromised and diluted by Liouville's theorem, by incoherent and coherent space charge effects, and by intrabeam scattering. The transition between space charge and scattering is presently not fully captured in simulations or theories.

The brightness of hadron beams is advanced worldwide by major new projects in Nuclear Physics, including HIAF in China, FAIR in Germany, and the EIC in the US. These flagship projects. Along with the Gamma factory proposed at CERN, drive forward more complex and more efficient injection schemes, such as 2- or 3-plane injection, as well as advanced beam cooling methods. Emerging and evolving cooling techniques are more flexible and/or more powerful, with high-energy bunched-beam electron cooling, optical stochastic cooling, laser cooling, and coherent electron cooling figuring among the frontier techniques.

Crystalline beams or Bose-Einstein-condensate beams could reach an ultimate level of brightness.

Bright beams are also fundamental for realizing a nuclear clock as foreseen in the HITHOR project [18], where, by using highly charged ^{229}Th ions—especially the one-electron state $^{229}\text{Th}^{89+}$ —the nuclear hyperfine mixing is exploited, which enhances nuclear excitation rates by up to a millionfold. This approach, enabled by the advanced trapping facilities at GSI, will allow the first laser excitation of a nucleus, ushering in a new era of precision timekeeping and fundamental physics exploration.

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9 Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
AD	Antiproton Decelerator at CERN
BNL	Brookhaven National Laboratory on Long Island, U.S.A.
CERN	European Organization for Nuclear Research in Geneva, Switzerland
CSNS	Chinese Spallation Neutron Source in Guangdong, P.R. China
CSR	Cryogenic Storage Ring at MPI Heidelberg
ESR	Experimental Storage Ring at GSI
FAIR	Facility for Antiproton and Ion Research at GSI
HIAF	High Intensity Heavy-ion Accelerator Facility at IMP
IBS	Intrabeam Scattering
IMP	Institute of Modern Physics – Chinese Academy of Science
IHEP	Institute of High Energy Physics - Chinese Academy of Science
LINAC4	H ⁻ linac at CERN
PALLAS	Paul laser cooling acceleration system at Munich’s Ludwig-Maximilians University
PS	Proton Synchrotron at CERN
PSB	Proton Synchrotron (PS) Booster at CERN
RCS	Rapid Cycling Synchrotron
RF	Radiofrequency
RHIC	Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider at BNL
SPS	Super Proton Synchrotron at CERN